

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF YOUNG FAMILY PROBLEMS

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Research of socio-psychological features of young family problems for all peoples remains one of the current issues of psychology. No matter how large-scale scientific research on the problems of family life is carried out in social psychology, there are still insufficiently studied aspects of it. Among these, it is appropriate to include research on the occurrence of conflicts between spouses in young families. In this regard, many psychologists have conducted scientific research.

In particular, A.V.Shabaeva conducted scientific research on the social-psychological aspects of leadership in marriage and proved that the gender model of marriage in Muslim families serves to increase the role of the spouse in the family. It is explained that the leadership relationship of the couple is determined by the age, gender and ethnic origin of the couple, as well as the socio-economic conditions of family life.

According to the obtained data, it was shown that all the couples participating in the research demonstrated four types of family: traditional, egalitarian, non-traditional, ambivalent family. Factors determining the choice of a particular type are related to: age, gender, ethnic origin and territorial residence, as well as the personal characteristics of the head of the family and their value orientation.

The author says that the modern leadership model rejects "gender asymmetry in marriage" and women's rights are not violated. In addition, this model of family relations reduces gender conflicts; arises from the need to redistribute the traditional roles of men and women and therefore strengthens the institution of the family.

In his research, A.G.Svyashyennik focused on the culture of family relationships of people belonging to the Christian religion, and pointed out that the young bride and groom are not physically, psychologically, and spiritually and morally ready to start a family and family relationships at a certain level (the bridegroom's or the bride's we will see that conflict in family relationships, their intensification, and ultimately the breakdown of the family are covered by real-life examples and religiously based analysis.

If the culture of interpersonal relations is formed in the family, it creates an opportunity for family members to realize their desires and abilities to find their place and value in society. If family relations are not sufficiently formed or are not formed, then various problems and conflicts will arise. Harmony is lost in the family and an unpleasant psychological atmosphere is created in it. Family members cannot find their place in society either. Most importantly, this situation has a negative impact on children's development.

In his research, G.Roland singled out the necessary communicative qualities for young married couples to be satisfied with the interpersonal relationship in their family: 1. Sociability. 2. High mutual understanding in the family. 3. Sexual satisfaction of couples. 4. Availability of emotional support and trust. 5. Viewing "home" as a place that defines family unity.

We can clearly see the evidence of our above opinions from the results of research conducted by psychologists from far away countries. In a survey of 266 family counselors (specialists) in the United States during the survey period, they reported that 9 out of 10 families who came to them for help. They said that there are many difficulties in their relationship. Among these difficulties: incompatibility of ideas and professions - 86.6%, problems related to children and their education - 45.7%, problems related to sexual relations - 43.7%, problems without a financial solution - 37%, cultural problems - 37.6%, relationship with in-laws - 28.4%, mistrust between spouses - 26.6%, household issues - 16.7% , mental and physical abuse - 15.6%.

American researchers V. Metyuza and K. Mikhanovich have studied exactly such problems, i.e., the normal course of relations between husband and wife. They have shown more than ten necessary differences between happy and unhappy families (conditionally). These include: inequality in the relationship between husband and wife in the family; not understanding each other well; to speak angrily; feeling humiliated; neglect; despair; insecurity; to cause quarrels; disagreement with each other, demands for attention are important factors that cause unhappiness in the family.

Based on the above information, it can be concluded that, according to most psychologists, there are insufficient psychological conditions for family happiness in conflict families. This indicates that the qualities and qualities of a couple's relationship, which provide a healthy psychological environment in a young family, are not sufficiently formed.

List of used literature:

1. Келли Дж. Психология личности: теория личностных конструкторов. Санкт -Петербург, 2000, -356 с.

2. Винивидова Е. П. Структура понимания конфликтной ситуации молодыми супругами с разным стажем совместной жизни: диссертация ... кандидата психологических наук [Место защиты: Кур. гос. ун-т]. - Б. м., 2012. - 130 с.
3. Дзагкоев А. К. Молодая семья в современных условиях: На материале Республики Северная Осетия-Алания. Автореф. дисс. к. соц. н. М, 2000, -42 с.
4. Лидовская Н.Н. Взаимоотношения супругов в незарегистрированном браке. диссертация ... кандидата психологических наук. Санкт-Петербург, 2009. -212 с.
5. Alimardonova R.K. Yosh kelin-kuyov o'rtasidagi sog'lom psixologik munosabatlarni ta'minlashning ijtimoiy-etnik asoslari. Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) dissertatsiyasi. T.: 2022, 130 b.

